

Direct torque control and dynamic performance of induction motor using fractional order fuzzy logic controller

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ABSTRACT

Conventional direct torque control (DTC) is one of the best control systems for regulating the torque of an induction motor (IM). However, the DTC's enormous waves in flux and torque cause acoustic noise that degrades control performance, especially at low speeds due to the DTC's low switching frequency. Direct torque control systems, which focus just on torque and flux, have been proposed as a solution to these problems. In order to improve DTC control performance, this work introduces a fractional-order fuzzy logic controller method. The objective is to analyze this technique critically with regard to its efficacy in reducing ripple, its tracking speed, its switching loss, its algorithm complexity, and its sensitivity to its parameters. Simulation in MATLAB/Simulink verifies the anticipated control approach's performance.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Takahashi and Noguchi proposed direct torque control (DTC) for AC machines in 1986 [1]. In comparison to the field orientating control (FOC) technique, DTC has attracted aid of multiple academics since its several benefits, including its simple structure, quick dynamic reaction, and lower reliance on machine parameters. Dynamic variation performance are the primary issues with traditional DTCs [2]–[4]. The presence of hysteresis device in the standard DTC scheme [5] is well established as the action of switch frequency changes. Several solutions have been proposed to alleviate DTC limitations, such as using artificial intelligence (AI) algorithms [6]–[8]. Several academics have proposed and developed the space vector modulation (SVM) technique to eliminate torque and flux ripples by operating the inverter at a continuous switching frequency. To calculate reference voltage vector components that are adjusted by the SVM unit to produce inverter switching states, the SVM-DTC replaces two hysteresis controllers with two proportional integral (PI) controllers [9]. In terms of ripples, this control approach increases DTC performance. The usage of PI controllers, on the other hand, necessitates a thorough understanding of the controlled system's specific model [10], [11].

Furthermore, selecting controller gains is a difficult task. In most cases, gain values calculated using simulation do not perform well in practice. When interruptions, uncertainty, and parameter change are present, PI controllers have limited functionality. As a consequence, the system's dynamic and stability will be justified [12], [13]. To overcome the restrictions of the refereed methods, strong nonlinear control systems for induction motor control, such as the fuzzy logic controller (FLC) [12], have been developed. The initial contribution of this study is the implementation of a FLC for an induction motor, which is motivated by the

discussion above. This controller was chosen because of its ease of use and minimal cost of implementation [14], [15]. Figure 1 depicts the block diagram of fractional order FLC based DTC of the induction motor.

Figure 1. Block diagram of fractional order fuzzy logic controller (FOFLC) based DTC of the induction machine

2. DYNAMIC MODELING OF INDUCTION MOTOR

To model the three-phase induction motor, certain assumptions are made: each stator winding is distributed along the air gap to bring out sinusoidal mmf [16]. The rotor has a squirrel cage shape, and the airspace between both the machines is consistent. Coils are the same in both cases. The losses due to stator winding saturation, hysteresis, and eddy currents are not considered [17], [18]. Indeed, the induction motor’s dynamic behavior in the stationary action (α, β) defined as below. In the stationary reference (α, β), the stator voltage vector V_s is represented by (1), (2), (3):

$$V_{s\alpha} = \frac{d\phi_{s\alpha}}{dt} + R_s i_{s\alpha} \tag{1}$$

$$V_{s\beta} = \frac{d\phi_{s\beta}}{dt} + R_s i_{s\beta} \tag{2}$$

$$\bar{V}_s = \frac{d\bar{\phi}_s}{dt} + R_s \bar{i}_s \tag{3}$$

where $(V_{s\alpha}, V_{s\beta})$, $(\phi_{s\alpha}, \phi_{s\beta})$, and $(i_{s\alpha}, i_{s\beta})$ are the voltage, stator flux, and stator current components in the concordant reference (alpha, beta), respectively. The stator resistance is denoted by R_s . In the concordance reference (α, β), the time derivative of the rotor flow is as (4), (5):

$$\frac{d\phi_{\{r\alpha\}}}{dt} = -R_{\{r\}} i_{\{r\alpha\}} - \omega_{\{m\}} \phi_{\{r\beta\}} \tag{4}$$

$$\frac{d\phi_{\{r\beta\}}}{dt} = -R_{\{r\}} i_{\{r\beta\}} - \omega_{\{m\}} \phi_{\{r\alpha\}} \tag{5}$$

where $(\phi_{r\alpha}, \phi_{r\beta})$ and $(i_{r\alpha}, i_{r\beta})$ are the flux and current components of the rotor, respectively. The rotor resistance and motor speed are represented by R_r and ω_m , respectively. The components of the stator flux vector ϕ_s can be represented as (6), (7), (8):

$$\phi_{\{s\alpha\}} = L_{\{s\}} i_{\{s\alpha\}} + M i_{\{r\alpha\}} \tag{6}$$

$$\phi_{\{s\beta\}} = L_s i_{s\beta} + M i_{r\beta} \tag{7}$$

$$\bar{\phi}_s = L_s \bar{i}_s + M \bar{i}_r \tag{8}$$

The flux vector of the stator ϕ_s and its elements can be represented as (9), (10), (11):

$$\phi_{r\alpha} = L_r i_{r\alpha} + M i_{s\alpha} \quad (9)$$

$$\phi_{r\beta} = L_r i_{r\beta} + M i_{s\beta} \quad (10)$$

$$\bar{\phi}_r = L_r \bar{i}_r + M \bar{i}_s \quad (11)$$

The stator, rotor, and mutual inductance are represented by L_s , L_r , and M , respectively. The following is a brief description of mechanical motor movements.

$$J \frac{d\omega_m}{dt} = T_{em} - T_l - f\omega_m \quad (12)$$

The torque, the load torque, rotor momentum, and viscous frictional force are represented as T_{em} , T_l , J and f , respectively. The motor's electromagnetic torque can be calculated using the formula (13).

$$T_{em} = \frac{3}{2} N_p (\phi_{s\alpha} i_{s\beta} - \phi_{s\beta} i_{s\alpha}) \quad (13)$$

The pole pairs are denoted by N_p . The state model of the induction motor is described by the time derivative of the stator current and flux components, as shown (14), (15), (16), (17).

$$\frac{di_{s\alpha}}{dt} = -\frac{1}{\sigma} \left(\frac{1}{T_r} + \frac{1}{T_s} \right) i_{s\alpha} - \omega_m i_{s\alpha} + \frac{1}{\sigma L_s T_r} \phi_{s\alpha} + \frac{\omega_m}{\sigma L_s} \phi_{s\beta} + \frac{1}{\alpha L_s} v_{s\alpha} \quad (14)$$

$$\frac{di_{s\beta}}{dt} = -\frac{1}{\sigma} \left(\frac{1}{T_r} + \frac{1}{T_s} \right) i_{s\beta} - \omega_m i_{s\beta} + \frac{1}{\sigma L_s T_r} \phi_{s\beta} + \frac{\omega_m}{\sigma L_s} \phi_{s\alpha} + \frac{1}{\beta L_s} v_{s\beta} \quad (15)$$

$$\frac{d\phi_{s\alpha}}{dt} = v_{s\alpha} + R_s i_{s\alpha} \quad (16)$$

$$\frac{d\phi_{s\beta}}{dt} = v_{s\beta} + R_s i_{s\beta} \quad (17)$$

3. CONTROL METHOD

3.1. Design of field orientating control

The FOC is very much famous to understand the derivative operator. The numerical expression for fractional order proportional integral (FOPI) is

$$c(s) = kp + \frac{Ki}{s^\lambda} \quad (18)$$

λ is range of (0,1). If $\lambda \geq 2$ is transformed to high-order expression is equal to PI controller. The F.O is described in (18) is common character of PI controller. To resolve the issues in fractional order fuzzy logic (FOFL) controller the effective filters can be used. The fitting range is (ω_b , ω_h). The function of fractional order is

$$K(s) = \left[\frac{1 + \frac{as}{b\omega_a}}{1 + \frac{bs}{b\omega_h}} \right]^\lambda \quad (19)$$

where $0 \leq \lambda \leq 1$; $s = j\omega$, $a \geq 0$; $b \geq 0$, and

$$K(s) = \left(\frac{as}{b\omega_a} \right)^\lambda \left(1 + \frac{-bs+b}{bs^2+a\omega_h s} \right)^\lambda \quad (20)$$

In the frequency range $\omega_b \geq \omega \geq \omega_h$ by using a "Taylor-series" expansion, we obtain

$$K(s) = \left(\frac{as}{b\omega_a} \right)^\lambda \left(1 + (s) + \frac{\lambda(\lambda-1)}{2} P^2(s) \dots \right) \quad (21)$$

where

$$F(s) = \left(1 + \frac{-bs+b}{bs^2+a\omega_h s}\right) \tag{22}$$

It is then found that

$$s^\lambda = \frac{(b\omega_a)^\lambda a^\lambda}{a^\lambda(1+(s) + \frac{\lambda(\lambda-1)}{2} p^2(s) \dots)} \left(\frac{1+as/b\omega_a}{1+bs/b\omega_b}\right)^\lambda \tag{23}$$

it leads to

$$s^\lambda = \frac{(b\omega_a)^\lambda a^\lambda}{a^\lambda(1+\lambda P(s))} \left(\frac{1+as/b\omega_a}{1+bs/b\omega_b}\right)^\lambda \tag{24}$$

Thus, the FOC is defined as (25).

$$s^\lambda \approx \left(\frac{b\omega_a}{b}\right)^\lambda \left(\frac{ds^2+b\omega_h s}{d(1-\lambda)s^2+b\omega_h s+d\lambda}\right) \left(\frac{1+bs/d\omega_b}{1+ds/d\omega_h}\right)^\lambda \tag{25}$$

As shown in (21) is proportionate when all the poles are on LHS of s-plane. The poles should follow the stability condition.

$$b(1-\lambda)s^2 + a\omega_h s + b \tag{26}$$

Hence, all the poles of (24) are stable within the limit of (ω_l, ω_h) .

$$K(s) = \lim N \rightarrow \infty F_N(s) = \prod_F^N \lim N \rightarrow \infty = -N \frac{1+s/\omega'_k}{1+s/\omega_k} \tag{27}$$

According to the algorithmic distribution of real zeros and poles, the zero and pole of rank k can be written as (28).

$$\omega'_k = \left(\frac{b\omega_a}{a}\right)^{\frac{\lambda-2k}{2N+1}}, \omega_k = \left(\frac{b\omega_b}{a}\right)^{\frac{\lambda+2k}{2N+1}} \tag{28}$$

Hence final model can be stated as (29).

$$s^\lambda \approx \left(\frac{b\omega_a}{b}\right)^\lambda \left(\frac{ds^2+b\omega_h s}{d(1-\lambda)s^2+b\omega_h s+d\lambda}\right) = -N \frac{1+s/\omega'_k}{1+s/\omega_k} \tag{29}$$

The negative poles in real part for $0 \leq \lambda \leq 1$. The poles in (27) is in range of (ω_l/ω_h) . The (27) is approximated by uninterrupted -time coherent simulation. It is configured and ordered in the system depicts in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Structure of FOPI controller

3.2. Design of fuzzy logic controller

A simple FLC’s base level is seen in Figure 3. FLC is made up of input and output variables, as well as fuzzy inference, defuzzification, and fuzzification rules [19]–[21]. The FLC block diagram is shown in Figure 3. Seven membership functions are used to construct the fuzzy sets. A membership function for generating a fuzzy set is selected and created. Figure 4(a) and (b) depicts a FIS with inputs error and error change. Figure 5(a) and (b) depicts the output membership functions ΔKp and ΔKi . In order to improve the inference [22]. Figure 6 depicts the FOFL controller’s construction. Figure 7 depicts a proposed control technique with a new FOFL.

Figure 3. Structure of FL controller

(a)

(b)

Figure 4. Membership functions of error and change in error (a) membership functions of error and (b) membership functions of CE

Figure 5. Membership functions of adjusted gains (a) membership functions of Δk_i and (b) membership functions for ΔK_p

Figure 6. Design of proposed FOFLC

Figure 7. Control strategy of FOFLC

4. LEARNING PART

FLC works well in closed loop feedback systems, especially whenever the i/p and o/p are non-linear. Input errors and a gain value for the K_p and K_i terms are used by classical controllers like FOC [23], [24]. As a result, the controller action falls short of the standard for complex, non-linear systems. Instead of a fixed gain, the dynamic gain value for the K_p , complete terms, and derivatives might be used. Changing a FOPI control structure’s dynamic gain enhances controller’s performance and quickly remains stable system output during variance and noise. In light of these issues, an FLC system with a FOC is proposed [25]. The FOFL system incorporates the FLC and FOF controller’s functionality. The FLC is set up in this controller scheme to calculate the proportional scale factor 'E' using the system error and error derivatives as inputs[9]. In full, these scale factors will be used to change the amount of controller gain in each sample interval. The structure of FOFL control mechanism is seen in Figure 8 [5]. FLC creates the multiplier for proportional and integral terms using error and its derivative in the proposed system of control, and these values are then utilized to update the FOFL controller’s gain settings. The K_p and K_i signal gain levels for the FOFL controller are estimated using the calculations in (30), (31).

$$K_p = k_p + \Delta K_p \tag{30}$$

$$K_i = k_i + \Delta k_i \tag{31}$$

Here k_p and k_i are the determinate gain values. The flowchart of the planned method is depicted in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Flowchart for proposed system

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

MATLAB/Simulink was used to do dynamic modelling and simulation of a three-phase induction motor. The model was put to the test for two different induction motor ratings: low and high. And also, it examined No load conditions, constant load condition and variable load conditions. The results are discussed in the following cases.

5.1. At no load conditions

Figure 9 shows the torque and speed characteristics of the PI and FOFLC. The speed and torque parameters of traditional PI and FLC are shown in Figure 9. When the FOFLC is added to the simulation model and both results are taken at the same time, it appears that the rising time lowers. FOLC has a rise time of 0.3350 seconds, while PI has a rise time of 0.3435 seconds. There is a minor variation in T_r , M (overshoot), and T_s that is not visible in the graph. The torque and speed characteristics variation of IM for all controller is shown in Figures 10 and 11 respectively.

Figure 9. Torque and speed characteristics of PI and FOFL controller

Figure 10. Speed characteristics of IM using all controllers

Figure 11. Torque characteristics of IM using all controllers

5.2. At constant load

The torque and speed parameters are shown in Figure 12. There is a drop in torque and speed when a 14 Nm load is applied rapidly at 1.5 sec. Following the occurrence of the initial transient, the motor settles at 1.9466 sec with the FOFL controller and 1.8787 sec with the PI controller. To make a fair comparison, the PI controller is tuned at rated circumstances. When the motor is started with a constant of 14 Nm, the simulated results are shown in Figure 10. The drive’s performance in comparison to traditional PI and FOLC-based drive systems. When a constant load is applied suddenly, the PI controller takes longer to reach the desired speed than the fuzzy controller. The torque and speed characteristics variation of IM for all controller is shown in Figures 13 and 14 respectively.

Figure 12. Torque and speed characteristics of PI and FOFL controller

Figure 13. Speed characteristics of IM using all controllers

Figure 14. Torque characteristics of IM using all controllers

5.3. At variable load

When using a PI controller, the speed response peaks at 0.6 seconds, but when using a FOFL controller, the speed response is swift and smooth, as illustrated in Figure 15. Using a FOFL controller, the motor speed follows its reference with zero steady-state error and a quick reaction. The PI controller, on the other hand, exhibits steady-state inaccuracy when the initial current is high. It should be noted that the load conditions have an impact on the speed response. A PI controller with changeable operating circumstances has this disadvantage. In terms of rising time and steady state error, the FOFL controller outperforms. The torque and speed characteristics variation of IM for all controller is shown in Figures 16 and 17 respectively.

Figure 15. Torque and speed characteristics of PI and FOFL controller

Figure 16. Speed characteristics of IM using all controllers

Figure 17. Torque Characteristics of IM using all controllers

Tables 1 and 2 compare the performance of PI and FOFL controllers during steady state and transient operation in terms of T_r , M (overshoot), and T_s for various load circumstances. The tables show that FOFLC has a faster rise time, settling time, and less overshoot than PI under various load circumstances. As a result, the FOFLC controller outperforms the PI controller. This demonstrates the three-phase induction motor's ability to adjust speed and deliver a precise and fast reaction with no overshoot and no steady state inaccuracy. The current development of the stator is seen in Figures 18(a) and (b). The stator current in the FOFL controller-based IM has an excellent sinusoid waveform, but the stator current in the traditional DTC has significant harmonics.

Table 1. Dynamic performance comparison between PI and FOFLC during transient operation

Control strategies	Rise Time(sec)	%Overshoot	Settling Time (sec)
PI	0.3435	1.1793	0.5163
FLC	0.335	0.9454	0.4731
FOPI	0.2457	0.7018	0.3380
FOFL	0.2189	0.6059	0.2962

Table 2. Dynamic performance comparison between PI and FOFLC during transient operation

Control strategies	Rise Time(sec)	%Overshoot	Settling Time (sec)
PI	0.5516	0.629	1.9466
FLC	0.4825	0.5987	1.8787
FOPI	0.2873	0.4564	1.7641
FOFL	0.2641	0.4064	1.6423

Figure 18. 3- ϕ stator current for 18 (a) traditional controller and 18 (b) FOFLC based on IM

6. CONCLUSION

MATLAB/Simulink software is used to model the closed loop control system of a FOFLC and a three-phase SVPWM VSI in this paper. It can be inferred that using FOFLC for various load conditions enhances and smooths out motor torque and stator current ripples. The simulation findings proved the FOFLC controller's excellent dynamic performance and robustness during the transient period and under abrupt loads. The proposed intelligent controller outperformed the parameter fixed PI controller, according to the results. In the case of a PI controller, more and more trial and error are required to achieve optimal speed control of an IM drive.

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